

The photochromism of 1-alkyl-2-(arylo)imidazoles trapped in water pool by AOT-heptane reverse micelle

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Abstract : 1-Alkyl-2-(arylo)imidazole exists in *trans*-geometry about -N=N- group at ambient condition. UV light irradiation in (363–371 nm) in solution phase of the compounds has changed their *trans*-geometry to *cis*-structure. The *cis*-to-*trans* isomerisation proceeds slowly in visible light irradiation while it is appreciably fast on heating. The photoisomerisation rate is controlled by microenvironment of photochrome. In this work we have examined the influence of reverse micelle (AOT/*n*-heptane/water) on kinetics and mechanism of photoisomerisation of azoimidazoles. The effect of [AOT] and water pool size [*W*] on the quantum yields of *trans*-to-*cis* isomerisation are examined. The rate of *trans*-to-*cis* transformation is increased by 5–66% with increase in [AOT]. The quantum yield is also increased by 30–120% under identical condition. The activation energy (E_a) of *cis*-to-*trans* is calculated and in presence of reverse micelle the activation energy is reduced. It justifies the enhancement of rate.

Keywords : Photochromism, aryloimidazole, reverse micelle (AOT), activation energy.

Introduction

Photochromism is defined as light induced reversible isomerisation of molecules in which each isomer has separate absorption spectral properties. This property is sensitive to the solution structures, solvent polarity, viscosity, presence of foreign molecules or ions in the media. In general, increase in solvent polarity or use of protic solvents enhances kinetic energy barrier of *cis*-*trans* isomerisation of photochrome^{1–4}. Recently, role of ionic liquid has been explored on the kinetics and mechanism of photoisomerisation⁵. Presence of suitable photosensitizers may also influence the kinetics and energy barrier^{6,7} of the process. Thanks to this property, the photochromes have been employed for different uses and applications, such as in light controlled polymers⁸, liquid crystals⁹, surfaces¹⁰, and catalysts¹¹, and were more recently found to be promising in controlling the structural and functional changes in biomolecules^{12,13}. Photo-magnetism of substituted azobenzenes has been established by theoretical calculation¹⁴. Photochromic doped sol-gel systems develop novel materials for information processing and for other optical applications¹⁵. Polypeptide con-

taining azobenzenes show reversible photoinduced random coil/ α -helix conformational transitions, the extent of the photoresponse is depending on solvent composition¹⁶. Studies on photochromism of spiropyrans, spirooxazines, naphthopyran, azobenzenes etc. have been carried out in different organic solvents^{1–3}, polymer matrix^{17–24}, membranes²⁵, monolayers²⁶, clay materials²⁷, micelles and reverse micelles^{28,29}. Photochrome implanted in polymer film shows different sensitivity to UV light irradiation^{30–38}.

For the last several years we have been used light as stimulus to follow the isomerisation of 1-alkyl-2-(arylo)imidazoles (Scheme 1) and some of their metal complexes^{39–44}. Aryloimidazole, a class of heterocyclic azo compound, has been extensively used as ligands for the study of coordination complexes of different metal ions^{45–55}. In this article we report the effect of microenvironment originated by adding organized assemblies like, AOT (sodium bis-(2-ethylhexyl)sulfosuccinate), a reverse micelle, in water pool of solution on the photoisomerisation of aryloimidazoles. The surfactant solubilized water provides a medium with unique properties for

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Scheme 1. Isomerization of 1-alkyl-2-(arylo)imidazole.

reactions involving polar substrates and it has been reported that water pools in the reverse micelle cavity have much lower micropolarity⁵⁶, which can influence kinetic features. In particular, reverse AOT micelles have been studied extensively during the past decades^{57,58}. The behavior of molecule at an interface between two bulk media and is often significantly different from that in either of the bulk media. Since the polarity and viscosity at the interface are often very much different from those of the bulk media, the structure, dynamics and reactivity of an organic or bio-molecule at an interface differ markedly from those observed in the bulk.

Experimental

Reagents/Materials :

1-Alkyl-2-(arylo)imidazoles were synthesized by reported procedure⁴⁹. Imidazole, aniline, *p*-toluidine were of analytical reagent grade collected from SRL, India. Sodium bis(2-ethylhexyl)sulfosuccinate (AOT) collected from Sigma-Aldrich. All other chemicals and solvents were reagent grade as received. *n*-Heptane and 2-propanol (SRL, India) were distilled before use. Aqueous solutions were prepared in deionised and double distilled water.

Preparation of the reverse micelle medium :

To prepare a stock reverse micelle solution of strength 1.0 mol dm^{-3} , required amount of anionic surfactant, AOT was dissolved in apolar solvent, *n*-heptane. Solutions of different concentrations were prepared by accurate dilution of stock solution with *n*-heptane. Ligand solution in propanol and required amount of water was added to the AOT solution and shaken to obtain a transparent solution and *W* value that can be regarded as a reverse micelle system.

Photometric measurements :

Spectroscopic data were obtained using the following instruments : UV-Vis spectra from Perkin-Elmer-Lambda 25 spectrophotometer; photoexcitation has been carried out using Perkin-Elmer LS-55 spectrofluorimeter. Absorption spectra were taken with a Perkin-Elmer-Lambda 25 UV/Vis spectrophotometer in a $1 \times 1 \text{ cm}$ quartz optical cell maintained at $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The light source of a Perkin-Elmer LS 55 spectrofluorimeter was used as an excitation light, with a slit width of 10 nm . An optical filter was used to cut off overtones when necessary. The absorption spectra of the *cis* isomers were obtained by extrapolation of the absorption spectra of a *cis*-rich mixture for which the composition is known from ^1H NMR integration. Quantum yields (ϕ) were obtained by measuring initial *trans*-to-*cis* isomerization rates (ν) in a well-stirred solution within the above instrument using the equation,

$$\nu = (\phi I_0/V)(1 - 10^{-\text{Abs}})$$

where I_0 is the photon flux at the front of the cell, V is the volume of the solution, and Abs is the initial absorbance at the azobenzene ($\phi = 0.11$ for $\pi\text{-}\pi^*$ excitation⁴²) under the same irradiation condition.

Results and discussion

The compounds :

1-Methyl-2-(phenylazo)imidazole (Pai-Me, **1a**), 1-methyl-2-(*p*-tolylazo)imidazole (Tai-Me, **1b**), 1-ethyl-2-(phenylazo)imidazole (Pai-Et, **2a**) and 1-ethyl-2-(*p*-tolylazo)imidazole (Tai-Et, **2b**) are used in this work (Scheme 2).

Scheme 2

Photochromism of azoimidazoles :

The absorption spectra are recorded in solution in 200–900 nm. The absorption band around 340–380 nm with a molar absorption coefficient on the order of $10^4 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and a tail extending into 450 nm are assigned to $\pi\text{-}\pi^*$ and $n\text{-}\pi^*$ transitions, respectively. The assignment

is also supported by theoretical calculations, as described elsewhere³⁹. Upon irradiation of light at λ_{\max} to propanol solution of the compound, the absorption spectrum changes as shown in Fig. 1. Upon repeated irradiation

upto 25 cycles the absorption modulation remains unchanged that signifies photo-stability of the molecule (Fig. 2). The intense peak at λ_{\max} decreases, which is accompanied by a slight increase at the tail portion of the

Fig. 1. Spectral changes of Tai-Me upon repeated irradiation in propanol solution at 362 nm at 3 min interval at 25 °C. Inset figure shows the spectra of *cis* and *trans* isomers of Tai-Me.

Fig. 2. Resistance to repeated irradiation of Tai-Me in 2-propanol solution upon UV light irradiation at 362 nm for 10 min followed by irradiation of visible light at 455 nm for 10 min.

spectrum around 470 nm until a stationary state is reached. Subsequent irradiation at the newly appeared longer wavelength peak reverses the course of the reaction and the original spectrum is recovered up to a point, which is another photostationary state under irradiation at the longer wavelength peak. It is observed that upon irradiation with UV light *trans-to-cis* photoisomerisation has proceeded and the *cis* molar ratio is reached to >95%. The absorption spectra of the *trans*-ligands changed with isosbestic points upon excitation (Fig. 1) into the *cis*-isomer. The ¹H NMR technique has been adopted to measure the percentage composition of the irradiated solution which sup-

ports the composition obtained from absorption spectra. The ¹H NMR signals of the aromatic ring protons are significantly shifted to upper field portion after the light irradiation. The quantum yields were measured for the *trans-to-cis* ($\phi_{t \rightarrow c}$) photoisomerisation of these compounds on irradiation of UV wavelength (Table 1). The $\phi_{t \rightarrow c}$ values are significantly dependent on nature of substituents. The Me substituent at azophenyl group (Pai-R to Tai-R) and Et substituent at N(1)-position (1-Me to 1-Et) both reduce $\phi_{t \rightarrow c}$ values. In general, increase in mass of the molecule reduces the rate of isomerisation, *trans-to-cis* (Table 1).

Table 1. Excitation wavelength (λ_{π, π^*}), rate of *trans* (t) \rightarrow *cis* (c) conversion and quantum yield ($\phi_{t \rightarrow c}$) of photoisomerisation in presence of reverse micelle

Compd.	AOT conc. (M)	Water pool (W)	Excitation wave length (nm)	Quantum yield	Isobestics (nm)	Rate $\times 10^8$ (s ⁻¹)	
				<i>trans-to-cis</i>			
Pai-Me	Nil	0	360	0.126	322, 431	2.354	
Tai-Me			362	0.116	321, 433	2.021	
Pai-Et			360	0.119	325, 433	2.183	
Tai-Et			363	0.104	325, 433	1.983	
Pai-Me	0.05	2.77	368	0.245	328, 457	3.61	
Tai-Me			367	0.231	334, 451	3.38	
Pai-Et			366	0.238	328, 454	3.54	
Tai-Et			367	0.226	331, 448	3.30	
Pai-Me	0.1	8.33	363	0.259	320, 476	3.79	
Tai-Me			371	0.248	329, 446	3.65	
Pai-Me			11.11	366	0.278	326, 445	3.91
Tai-Me				370	0.267	332, 444	3.84
Pai-Me	0.2	2.77	366	0.187	329, 455	2.87	
Tai-Me			367	0.176	327, 464	2.68	
Pai-Et			367	0.182	326, 455	2.80	
Tai-Et			366	0.173	330, 459	2.62	
Pai-Me	0.2	8.33	367	0.201	330, 441	3.02	
Tai-Me			368	0.191	331, 440	2.95	
Pai-Me			11.11	366	0.219	325, 448	3.20
Tai-Me				366	0.207	328, 441	3.14
Pai-Me	0.2	2.77	366	0.178	329, 451	2.71	
Tai-Me			366	0.168	329, 445	2.54	
Pai-Et			366	0.171	332, 448	2.60	
Tai-Et			368	0.163	326, 460	2.47	
Pai-Me	0.2	8.33	367	0.189	327, 457	2.90	
Tai-Me			366	0.181	330, 449	2.77	
Pai-Me			11.11	367	0.210	329, 458	3.12
Tai-Me				366	0.197	331, 444	3.06

Photochromism of azoimidazoles in reverse micelle media :

Photochromism is influenced by the medium – their polarity, viscosity, volume, mass and also on the nature of substituent on the photochrome. The covalent and non-covalent interaction amongst molecules may influence the physical, photophysical, catalytic, electrochemical properties. Molecular and supramolecular interactions may regulate photochromic activity of these molecules. The UV light (363–371 nm) is irradiated to the reverse micelle media of 1-alkyl-2-(arylo)imidazole and the rate of photoisomerisation changes are recorded in Table 1 and representative figures are given in Figs. 3 and 4. In reverse micelle media, sodium bis(2-ethylhexyl)-sulfosuccinate (AOT), the rate of isomerisation is increased by 5–66% with [AOT] than that of free molecular data. The quantum yield of the isomerisation is also increased (30–120%) which suggests reduction in energy barrier in the isomerisation process. Upon water addition to AOT/*n*-heptane the reversed micelle structure is developed (Scheme 3). It is constituted by spherical nanodroplets of

water dispersed in the organic solvent (*n*-heptane) with AOT molecules coating the interface between the water droplet and the oil^{59–65}. This interface is especially important due to its mild polarity; polar organic molecules prefer to stay at such a region of the reversed micelles, on either the hydrophilic or hydrophobic side⁶².

This reaction rate has been also studied in AOT reverse micelle cavity and it is found that the rate increases compared to 2-propanol solution only. In the reverse micelle cavity of AOT, the isomerisation occurs in water present in a reverse micelle cavity, referred to ‘water pool’. The effect of variation of AOT concentrations on isomerisation rate have been studied at different values of *W* (*W* = 2.77–11.11) (Table 1) and the variation of AOT (0.05 and 0.2 mol dm⁻³) at the high value of *W* (=11.11) have a significant effect on quantum yield (Fig. 5). 1-Alkyl-2-(arylo)imidazoles are insoluble in *n*-heptane and exists in propanol-water phase. So, the reaction only can take place either in the water pool or in the micellar interface or in both. Since the increase in AOT concentration at fixed *W* increases the micellar concentration

Fig. 3. Spectral changes of Pai-Me in presence of AOT reverse micelle (0.05 M, *W* = 2.77) upon repeated irradiation at 368 nm at 3 min interval at 25 °C.

Fig. 4. Spectral changes of Pai-Me in presence of AOT reverse micelle (0.2 M, W = 2.77) upon repeated irradiation at 366 nm at 3 min interval at 25 °C.

Scheme 3

Fig. 5. Influences of the quantum yield ($\phi_{t \rightarrow c}$) by the AOT concentration : (a) Pai-Me ($W = 11.11$), (b) Pai-Me ($W = 2.77$).

and hence the repulsion of reactants will be increased. The increase in rate and quantum yield with W (Fig. 6) because the area of the interface increases and hence greater number of molecule will get the chances for excitation.

The effect of variation of W on the rate and quantum yield at fixed AOT surfactant concentration and other variables have been studied (Table 1). On increasing W , the reactants are displaced into the water pool and at $W = 12.63$, the reaction takes place mainly in the water pool, where there is very little surfactant effect on rate (Fig. 6). Another way we can say that as W is increased, the properties of water pool approach to bulk water.

Fig. 6. Change of the quantum yield ($\phi_{t \rightarrow c}$) value of Pai-Me with the change of water pool at 0.05 M AOT concentration.

Thermal isomerisation, *cis* \rightarrow *trans* :

The irradiation at ~ 360 nm to the solution of 1-alkyl-2-(arylo)imidazoles in propanol has transformed *trans* \rightarrow *cis*-isomer ($> 95\%$) and the same solution has been allowed to the visible light irradiation at 455 nm to transfer them to *trans*-isomer. The process is very slow. While the thermal change at dark is relatively fast (Fig. 7) and the reaction rate is characterized by a single exponential function. The unimolecular rate constant of the thermal backward isomerisation (k) was obtained by the analysis of the measured absorbance, $Abs(t)$, $Abs(t) = (Abs_t - Abs_c)e^{-kt} + Abs_c$ where Abs_c and Abs_t are absorbances corresponding to pure samples of *c* (*cis*) and *t* (*trans*) forms, respectively. The thermal *cis*-to-*trans* isomerisation rates were obtained by monitoring absorption changes intermittently for a *cis*-rich solution kept in the dark at constant temperature (T) in the range 298–313 K. The activation energy (E_a) and the frequency factor (A) were obtained from $\ln k = \ln A - E_a/RT$, where k is the measured rate constant, R is the gas constant, and T is temperature (Fig. 8). The values of the activation free energy (ΔG^*) and the activation entropy (ΔS^*) were obtained through the relationships,

$$\Delta G^* = E_a - RT - T\Delta S^*$$

and

$$\Delta S^* = [\ln A - 1 - \ln(k_B T/h)]/R$$

where k_B and h are Boltzmann's and Plank's constants, respectively.

The activation energy, E_a , of thermal isomerisation was determined by fitting the temperature dependent k values (Fig. 8) and the results are listed in Table 2. Data reveal that the activation energy (E_a) increases in the micelle phase (Fig. 9) and the thermal *cis*-to-*trans* isomerisation rate of the ligands are decreased by 20–40%. *Cis*-isomer is more polar than *trans*-1-alkyl-2-(arylo)imidazole. Hence *cis*-isomer is better stabilized in micelle phase and the thermal data support, indeed (Table 2). A cartoon in Scheme 3 explains the plausible mechanism of photoisomerisation of 1-alkyl-2-(arylo)imidazole in reverse micelle media.

Conclusion :

1-Alkyl-2-(arylo)imidazole isomerizes from the stable *trans*- to *cis*-isomer on light irradiation at the UV wavelength. The reverse, *cis*-to-*trans*, is very slow by light

Fig. 7. Spectral changes of Pai-Me during thermal process of *cis* (c) \rightarrow *trans* (t) in presence of AOT reverse micelle upon repeated irradiation at 368 nm at 5 min interval at 30 °C.

Fig. 8. The Eyring plots of rate constants of *cis*-to-*trans* thermal isomerisation of (a) Pai-Me and (b) Pai-Me in AOT reverse micelle (0.05 M, W = 11.11).

Fig. 9. Change of activation energy (E_a) with change of AOT concentration. (a) Pai-Me at 0.05 M AOT (W = 2.77), (b) Pai-Me at 0.10 M AOT (W = 2.77), (c) Pai-Me at 0.2 M AOT (W = 2.77).

Table 2. Rate and activation parameters for *cis* (c) \rightarrow *trans* (t) thermal isomerisation

Compd.	AOT conc. (M)	Water pool (W)	Temp. (K)	Rate of thermal c \rightarrow t conversion $\times 10^5$ (s $^{-1}$)	E_a (kJ mol $^{-1}$)	ΔH^* (kJ mol $^{-1}$)	ΔS^* (J mol $^{-1}$ K $^{-1}$)	ΔG^{*c} (kJ mol $^{-1}$)
Pai-Me	Nil	0	298	2.49	37.78	35.24	-195.32	93.44
			303	3.49				
			308	4.31				
			313	5.22				

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Table-2 (contd.)

Tai-Me			298	3.49	28.68	26.15	-223.23	92.67
			303	4.21				
			308	5.31				
			313	5.98				
Pai-Et			298	2.29	32.53	29.98	-214.06	93.76
			303	2.79				
			308	3.39				
			313	4.32				
Tai-Et			298	2.31	25.71	23.16	-236.78	93.72
			303	2.69				
			308	3.15				
			313	3.81				
Pai-Me	0.05	2.77	298	1.66	82.72	80.18	-66.42	99.97
			303	3.74				
			308	5.66				
			313	8.52				
Tai-Me			298	1.80	77.87	75.33	-82.14	99.80
			303	3.86				
			308	5.71				
			313	8.39				
Pai-Et			298	1.71	80.62	78.08	-73.24	99.90
			303	3.82				
			308	5.66				
			313	8.45				
Tai-Et			298	1.85	75.72	73.18	-89.12	99.73
			303	3.91				
			308	5.69				
			313	8.28				
Pai-Me		8.33	298	0.76	86.90	84.36	-59.77	102.17
			303	1.30				
			308	2.74				
			313	3.83				
Tai-Me			298	0.81	84.09	81.55	-68.75	102.03
			303	1.32				
			308	2.75				
			313	3.86				
Pai-Me		11.11	298	0.69	90.55	88.01	-28.93	96.63
			303	1.31				
			308	2.69				
			313	3.79				
Tai-Me			298	0.75	87.34	84.80	-39.24	96.49
			303	1.29				
			308	2.73				
			313	3.81				
Pai-Me	0.1	2.77	298	2.08	63.45	60.91	-129.11	99.38
			303	4.22				

Table-2 (contd.)

			308	5.73				
			313	7.31				
Tai-Me			298	2.21	60.46	57.92	-138.74	99.26
			303	4.23				
			308	5.83				
			313	7.25				
Pai-Et			298	2.12	62.79	60.25	-131.21	99.35
			303	4.18				
			308	5.81				
			313	7.29				
Tai-Et			298	2.32	57.70	55.16	-147.65	99.15
			303	4.26				
			308	5.86				
			313	7.18				
Pai-Me	8.33		298	1.05	66.13	63.59	-127.10	101.46
			303	1.39				
			308	2.76				
			313	3.46				
Tai-Me			298	1.07	65.35	62.81	-129.61	101.43
			303	1.40				
			308	2.82				
			313	3.45				
Pai-Me	11.11		298	0.97	71.38	68.84	-110.16	101.66
			303	1.35				
			308	2.81				
			313	3.52				
Tai-Me			298	1.01	68.62	66.08	-119.05	101.55
			303	1.37				
			308	2.79				
			313	3.48				
Pai-Me	0.2	2.77	298	2.23	60.17	57.63	-139.75	99.27
			303	4.19				
			308	5.85				
			313	7.24				
Tai-Me			298	1.67	56.60	54.12	-79.10	77.69
			303	2.84				
			308	3.95				
			313	5.06				
Pai-Et			298	2.31	58.28	55.74	-145.82	99.19
			303	4.21				
			308	5.91				
			313	7.19				
Tai-Et			298	2.61	52.71	50.17	-163.66	98.92
			303	4.30				
			308	6.02				
			313	7.22				

Table-2 (contd.)

Pai-Me	8.33	298	1.09	64.17	61.63	-133.37	101.37
		303	1.42				
		308	2.85				
		313	3.43				
Tai-Me		298	1.14	61.40	58.86	-142.33	101.27
		303	1.45				
		308	2.91				
		313	3.38				
Pai-Me	11.11	298	0.98	70.25	67.71	-113.73	101.6
		303	1.39				
		308	2.82				
		313	3.50				
Tai-Me		298	1.06	65.27	62.73	-129.93	101.44
		303	1.39				
		308	2.78				
		313	3.42				

and susceptible to heat. The isomerisation is dependent on the composition of the photochrome and the solution structure. The rate of photoisomerisation, *trans*-to-*cis* increases in reverse micelle phase AOT/*n*-heptane/water. It may be due to compartmentalization/confinement of photochrome in micro-sized water pool those stabilize the photochrome structure. Increase of size of water pool increases the rate of photoisomerisation process and hence the quantum yield.

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